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Effects of Inclusion and Diversity on Students' Relationship with One Another

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A school should be where students can be comfortable showing their true identity. Having a different race, religion, culture, ethnicity, beliefs, sexual orientation, or social status from the majority is not a hindrance to striving for academic success. Diverse learning helps students learn how to respect each other's differences, not only with their peers but also with everyone they meet.

There are many ways in which schools can promote inclusion and diversity among students. In the Philippines, it became controversial for those students that are members of the LGBTQIA+ cutting their hair following school policy, even against their will. Many believe this policy would result in discrimination, and their haircut has nothing to do with how they will perform in class. Instead, forcing them to do this will only cause losing their confidence and may affect their academic performance. Because of that, the Department of Education has released a memorandum called Gender-Responsive Basic Education Policy, enforcing school officials to protect students from discrimination and gender-related violence in school. Another way to support diversity and inclusion in the classroom is by not making them feel different. Teachers must be the first ones to promote this. They can start by using teaching strategies that cover all social identities. Letting these students embrace their individuality can be the first step. By doing that, they can freely express their true self and view the school as a safe and welcoming environment.

Inclusive education reduces the chance of bullying and exclusion among students, giving them a sense of sympathy for their peers. Having group activities help share diverse perspectives and can make them critical thinkers. Being inside one classroom makes them understand and observe one another. However, despite these benefits, some challenges need to be addressed. One of them is lack of facilities, equipment, and learning tools for inclusive education. Students with special needs require extra accommodation and consideration from the school. Promoting an inclusive environment cannot be achieved if teachers lack awareness and sensitivity. Students finding the setting uncanny is a normal reaction, but if the teachers did not do anything to clear the confusions in their minds, they might do or say something that can make someone feel rejected. Therefore, having skilled teachers is significant. Discrimination inside classrooms can be avoided when the teacher knows how to act on these actions.

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Healthy relationships between students can lead to academic success. When there is a positive environment inside the classroom, studying will be less demanding. Students will feel more motivated to go to school because they are accepted and respected. Support coming from the school officials play a vital role in achieving this. Above all, society is becoming more open to inclusivity. It can be taught not only inside the classroom but also at home. The world will soon be full of people who know how to respect each one's differences.

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